

Studies on the Colorimetric Determination of Silica in Rocks*, Part-I. An Investigation on the Ruggedness of the Differential Colorimetric Method of Determination

R. C. SARKAR and M. SANKAR DAS

Analytical Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay-400 085, India

Manuscript received 18 June 1979, revised 2 January 1980, accepted 21 May 1980

The differential technique of measurement of the absorbance of the less sensitive β -silico-12-molybdate complex was adopted for a precise colorimetric method for the determination of silica in rocks. In the development of the method a multivariant study was made to establish the robustness of the procedure. By the use of a permanent standard chromate solution as reference and two standard silica solutions of lower and higher concentrations to bracket the absorbance of the sample solution, a better precision of the method could be achieved. The method was employed successfully for the determination of silica in standard and other rocks containing appreciable amount of ferrous iron. Presence of phosphorus called for a small correction. The relative standard deviation of the method was around 0.4% in the concentration range of 40-70% SiO_2 .

DETERMINATION of silica continues to be a problem in rock analysis. It is an enigma. The rapid instrumental methods, on the one hand, seem to be unacceptable to a large number of analysts when high precision and accuracy of the measurements are required, while, on the other hand, the laborious and time-consuming gravimetric method, by sheer high frequency of usage, achieves a dubious aura of popularity as could be seen from a recent study¹. Of the rapid methods currently in use, the one by Shapiro and Brannock² is found to give results to a precision of about 1%. The method involving fusion of samples with lithium metaborate followed by determination of silica by atomic absorption measurement, as proposed by Suhr and Ingamells³ and Van Loon and Parisiss⁴, was evaluated and recommended by Abbey. But in a subsequent publication⁵ the same author concluded that the method was not really suitable at high concentrations of silica. The neo-classical approach consisting of gravimetry for the major portion of silica and spectrophotometry⁶ or atomic absorptiometry⁷ for the silica remaining in solution, seems to be the present trend towards improving the precision of silica determination. Use of organic flocculating agents has been recommended to hasten the coagulation and filtration of the bulk of the silica from acid solution.

Application of heteropoly silicomolybdate complex for the colorimetric determination of silica has received considerable attention. Optimisation of the experimental parameters to obtain a single species useful for accurate determination of silica has been discussed in detail in the earlier

studies⁸⁻¹⁵. Chalmers and Sinclair¹⁵ describe the use of acetone for intensifying and stabilising the coloured beta-molybdosilicate complex against fading and recommend the use of a permanent chromate standard prepared according to Swank and Mellon¹⁶ for higher precision by differential colorimetry. The instrumental parameters needed for improving the precision have been evaluated by Abbey⁶. The main limitation in this method appears to be the rate of colour fading.

A detailed statistical evaluation of all the chemical parameters is carried out to evolve a rugged procedure suitable for the precise analysis of silica in rocks, and is described in this paper. Its accuracy has been evaluated by the analysis of a set of International rock standards of wide chemical composition.

Experimental

(a) Equipment :

1. Beckman Expandomatic SS-2 pH meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes is used in the normal mode for pH measurement.
2. Beckman DU spectrophotometer and 1.00 cm cells are used for absorption measurements.

(b) Reagents :

All the reagents are of BDH AnalaR or E. Merck/S. Merck GR grade. All solutions are prepared with distilled water.

* Based on a paper presented at the symposium "Chemical Analysis of Geological Materials", Calcutta, 6-9 February, 1979.

1. 30% sodium hydroxide solution is prepared by dissolving 30 g sodium hydroxide pellets in about 50 ml water contained in a polyethylene beaker and diluting to 100 ml.

2. 6*N*-hydrochloric acid is prepared by diluting conc. hydrochloric acid of sp. gr. 1.18.

3. 2*N*-nitric acid is prepared by diluting conc. nitric acid of sp. gr. 1.42.

4. Potassium permanganate solution : 0.05*N* approx.

5. Ammonium molybdate solution. A 10% (W/V) solution is prepared using $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The mixture is warmed, if necessary, for complete solution, filtered and stored in a polyethylene bottle. The solution should be rejected on the appearance of turbidity.

6. 6*N*- H_2SO_4 is prepared by diluting conc. H_2SO_4 , sp. gr. 1.835.

7. 0.1*M* ammonium phosphate, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$.

8. Standard reference stock solution. 3.22×10^{-3} *M* potassium chromate in 0.1*M* ammonium phosphate buffer.

9. Working standard reference solution is prepared by diluting the chromate stock solution with 0.1*M* diammonium hydrogen phosphate solution. A set of such solutions, prepared with 8, 10, 12 ml, ... of the stock solution and made upto 100 ml, cover the silica contents in the range 40-70% in the samples. A solution prepared with 10 ml of the reference stock solution, has an absorbance equivalent to about 1.67 mg SiO_2 per 100 ml.

(c) *Preparation of standard silica solution :*

Take 5.0 ml of 30% NaOH solution (using a polythene pipette) in a nickel crucible of about 50 ml capacity, and evaporate to dryness on a hot plate. Weigh accurately by difference, about 100 mg of the standard silicate previously dried at 105°-110° and containing less than 70 mg SiO_2 . Place the sample on the solid bed of sodium hydroxide in the crucible. U.S. Bureau of Standard Feldspar No. 99 containing 68.66% SiO_2 is used in this work. Place the crucible in a circular opening made in a thick asbestos plate exposing the bottom half of the crucible to the flame. Cover the crucible and fuse the sample for 10 min at a temp of 700° approx. Spread the melt on the inner sides of the crucible while cooling. Add about 15 ml of water and gently swirl the crucible for dissolution and detachment of the melt from its inner surface. Fill the crucible to half its volume with water and place it on a steam bath under cover for about half an

hour. Alternatively, fill the crucible to about 40 ml with water and keep it overnight at room temperature. Transfer the contents quantitatively into a polythene beaker containing about 300 ml of water and 15.0 ml of 6*N*-hydrochloric acid or 6*N*- H_2SO_4 . Transfer the solution into a 500 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with water. Mix and store the solution in a polythene bottle. The solution so prepared should have a pH value around 1.2.

(d) *Preparation of sample and blank solutions :*

Follow the steps used for the preparation of the silica standard solution to prepare sample solutions from the finely ground (-200 mesh) and dried samples (at 105°-110°). Prepare more than one process blank to ensure that the blank readings are low and reproducible. Centrifuge or filter the solution if it is turbid.

Recommended differential colorimetric procedure :

1. Take suitable aliquots of the sample (20 ml containing 2-3 mg SiO_2) and standard silica into 100 ml flasks.

2. Dilute the solutions to about 70 ml with water.

3. Add 3.0 ml of 2*N*- HNO_3 and mix.

4. Add 0.05*N*- KMnO_4 dropwise till a purple colour persists (two drops may be sufficient) and wash down the neck of the flask.

5. Add 10.0 ml of the molybdate solution slowly into one of the flasks, swirling during the addition, dilute to mark with water, and mix.

6. After 10 min., measure the absorbance of the yellow solution against the chromate solution at 400 nm.

7. Follow steps 5 and 6 in the case of other solutions.

Note :

- (a) Measure the absorbances of a set of standard silica solutions of varied concentrations. Any sample examined shall be closely straddled by two standard solutions.
 - (b) Ensure that the interval between the time of colour development and measurement, is maintained the same for all the solutions.
 - (c) Measure any appreciable absorbance of the compensating sample solution (without the addition of molybdate) against blank for correcting the absorbance of the respective test solution. Also check the absorbances of the process blank solutions.
 - (d) The true value of SiO_2 in a silicate rock sample containing phosphate, can be obtained by applying a correction on the basis that the absorbance of 1 part P_2O_5 equals to that of 0.4 part SiO_2 (at 400 nm) which is obtained by actual experiment.
-

Calculation :

Obtain the silica content of the sample using the following expression,

$$\% \text{SiO}_2 = \left[L + (H - L) \times \frac{a_x - a_L}{a_H - a_L} \right] \times \frac{100}{W}$$

where L and H are the amounts of SiO_2 in the aliquots of the 'low standard' and the 'high standard', and W is that of the sample used for colour development and a_L , a_H and a_x are the corresponding absorbances.

Robustness of the Recommended Method :

The recommended procedure described above is

evolved after carrying out a series of experiments designed to identify and control those factors to which the procedure could be vulnerable.

A schedule for the study of seven factors in eight combinations, as described by Youden¹⁷ is adopted to establish the ruggedness of the procedure. The experimental design and the differences obtained in the values arising from deviations from predetermined conditions in one of the first set of experiments are given in Tables 1 and 2. It is clear that the time-dependent stability of the colour intensity, factor 'G' vs 'g', is poor. Hence the need for a closer control on this factor is indicated.

TABLE 1—EIGHT COMBINATIONS OF SEVEN FACTORS USED IN THE RUGGEDNESS TEST ; AN INITIAL STUDY

Combination No.	Vol. of 30% NaOH for fusion	Time of fusion	Temp. of soln. (kept for 10 min)	Normality of (15 ml)HCl for acidification	Volume of 3N-HNO ₃	Volume of 10% MoO ₄ ²⁻	Time interval before colour measurement	Result %SiO ₂
	A/a (ml)	B/b (min)	C/c (°C)	D/d (N)	E/e (ml)	F/f (ml)	G/g (min)	
1.	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	68.38
2.	A	B	c	D	e	f	g	72.19
3.	A	b	C	d	E	f	g	70.44
4.	A	b	c	d	e	F	G	64.77
5.	a	B	C	d	e	F	g	66.60
6.	a	B	c	d	E	f	G	64.06
7.	a	b	C	D	e	f	G	65.00
8.	a	b	c	D	E	F	g	69.14

A=7 B=15 C=30 D=7 E=3 F=12 G=15
a=5 b=10 c=20 d=5 e=2 f=10 g=10

Note : 1. A fixed volume of persulphate solution is added to each test solution.
2. See Ref. 17 for details of the schedule.

TABLE 2—RESULTS FROM THE RUGGEDNESS-TEST LAID DOWN IN TABLE 1

Factor (F)	Alternate levels of F	Average result* of 4 combinations %SiO ₂	Difference (D)	D ²
Amount of alkali 30%	7.0 ml	68.94	2.74	7.51
	5.0 ml	66.20		
Time of fusion	15 min	67.80	0.46	0.21
	10 min	67.34		
Temp. of dissolution	30°C	67.60	0.19	0.04
	20°C	67.79		
HCl added (15 ml)	7N	68.68	2.21	4.88
	5N	66.47		
HNO ₃ added (3N)	3.0 ml	68.00	0.86	0.74
	2.0 ml	67.14		
MoO ₄ ²⁻ used (10%)	12 ml	67.22	0.70	0.49
	10 ml	67.92		
Colour stability	15 min	65.55	4.04	16.32
	10 min	69.59		

* e.g., the effect of alkali at the 1st level 'A' corresponds to the average of the results from combination numbers 1 to 4 in Table 1; similarly the effect of time of fusion at the 2nd level 'b' corresponds to the average of the results of combination numbers 3, 4, 7 and 8.

Another factor which needs control is the quantity of sodium hydroxide used for fusing the sample. This factor controls the pH of the solution which in turn influences the formation of the alpha or beta form of the heteropoly acid. In comparison it is seen that some other factors such as the time of fusion, factor B; the temperature at which the sample solution is prepared, factor C; and the quantity of the molybdate added, factor 'E' have smaller influence on the results. Hence control of their critical parameters as well as some other possible variables are included in further factorial studies which led to a final set of experiments (Table 3). The observed deviations are given in Table 4. Since the final differences are small, the precision of the measurements is computed and found to be about 0.4% in the determination of silica in rocks at a concentration level of 67%.

Results and Discussion

A prerequisite for the colorimetric determination of silica is that it should remain in solution in the

TABLE 3—EIGHT COMBINATIONS OF SEVEN FACTORS USED TO TEST THE RUGGEDNESS OF THE RECOMMENDED ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF SILICA

Combination number	Volume of NaOH(30%, fusion for 10 min)	Extraction of the melt	Normality of HCl, (15 ml for acidification)	Volume of HNO ₃ (2N)	Amount of 0.05N-KMnO ₄ added in excess	Volume of MoO ₄ ²⁻ (10%)	Time interval before colour measurement	%SiO ₂ found
	A/a (ml)	B/b	C/c (N)	D/d (ml)	E/e (drops)	F/f (ml)	G/g (min)	
1.	4.5	C/W, O.N.	5.5	2.8	1	9.5	10	67.32
2.	"	"	6.5	"	2	10.5	12	67.52
3.	"	H/W, ¼ hr	5.5	3.2	1	"	"	67.51
4.	"	"	6.5	"	2	9.5	10	67.63
5.	5.5	C/W, O.N.	5.5	"	"	"	12	67.33
6.	"	"	6.5	"	1	10.5	10	67.12
7.	"	H/W, ¼ hr	5.5	2.8	2	"	"	67.51
8.	"	"	6.5	"	1	9.5	12	67.86
Final recommended condition	5.0	C/W, O.N.	6.0	3.0	1	10.0	10	67.50

C/W, O.N. = Extraction with cold water keeping overnight.
H/W, ¼ hr = Extraction with hot water keeping on steam bath for ¼ hour.

TABLE 4—RESULTS OBTAINED FROM THE RUGGEDNESS TEST AS LAID DOWN IN TABLE 3

Factor (F)	Alternate levels of F	Average results of 4 combinations % SiO ₂	Difference (D)	D*
Amount of alkali (30% NaOH)	4.5 ml	67.49	0.04	0.0016
	5.5 ml	67.45		
Condition of extraction	C/W, O.N.	67.31	0.31	0.0361
	H/W, ¼ hr.	67.62		
HCl added to bulk soln. (15 ml)	5.5N	67.41	0.37	0.1369
	6.5N	67.78		
HNO ₃ added to test soln. (3N)	2.8 ml	67.50	0.10	0.010
	3.2 ml	67.40		
Excess KMnO ₄ (0.05N)	1 drop	67.45	0.05	0.0025
	2 drops	67.50		
Molybdate solution (10%)	9.5 ml	67.51	0.10	0.010
	10.5 ml	67.41		
Colour stability (time)	10 min	67.40	0.15	0.0225
	12 min	67.55		

$$S. D. = \sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 \times 2}{7}} = 0.28$$

Coefficient of variation is 0.4% for a sample at the concn. level of 67% SiO₂.

reactive form as monosilicic acid¹⁸. The sample size, acidity, and the final volume are recommended to ensure this condition.

Addition of specified amounts of the reagents as described in this procedure, brings the final pH of the solution to the optimal range of 1.0-1.8¹⁴, which is considered most favourable for the formation of beta-silicomolybdic acid. The molybdate concentration is maintained between 0.05M and 0.06M. The formation of alpha-acid under these conditions is not expected as it is a slow process and is accelerated by higher pH at elevated temperature¹¹.

Precision of the results improves as the absorb-

ances of the standard and the sample approach each other, and hence the choice of two closely bracketing silica standards. It is, however, necessary to complete the absorbance measurement within 10-12 min to avoid colour fading. The rate of fading of the colour of the silicomolybdate complex during the next 30 min after the stipulated time of 10 min is found to be about 2%. The addition of permanganate ensures complete oxidation of ferrous to ferric state. The effects of interfering elements like As, Ge and V are neglected as their concentrations in the normal silicate rocks, are very low.

A number of standard rock samples with diverse chemical compositions have been analysed for their silica contents to check the accuracy and reproducibility of the method. The results are given in Table 5. By adherence to the recommended proce-

TABLE 5—ANALYSIS OF STANDARD ROCK SAMPLES

Standard sample	Recommended value %SiO ₂	Range of values found by present method %SiO ₂
1. PCC-1	41.90 ¹⁹	(i) 41.76 (ii) 41.84
2. AGV-1	59.00 ¹⁹	(i) 58.92 (ii) 59.26
3. GSP-1	67.38 ¹⁹	(i) 67.38 (ii) 67.37
4. MRG-1	39.24 ¹	(i) 39.23 (ii) 39.14
5. Trachyte (TKT)	67.66 ^a 67.10 ^b	(i) 67.38 (ii) 67.57

(a) By Shapiro and Brannock method.
(b) By Gravimetric method.

sure the relative standard deviation of the method is found to be within 0.4% in the concentration range 40-70% SiO₂.

References

- S. ABBEY, A. H. GILLIESON and GUY PERRAULT, "A report on the collaborative analysis of three Canadian rock samples for use as certified reference materials", Mineral Science Laboratories, MRP/MSL 75-132(TR), and Supplement-1 Nov. 1976, Geol. Surv. Canada.

SARKAR & DAS : STUDIES ON THE COLORIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF SILICA IN ROCKS, PART—I. ETC.

2. L. SHAPIRO and W. W. BRANNOCK, U. S. Geol. Surv. Bull., 1962, 1144-A, 1-56.
3. N. H. SUHR and C. O. INGAMILLS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 730-734.
4. J. C. VAN LOON and C. M. PARISSIS, *Analyst*, 1969, **94**, 1057-1062.
5. S. ABBEY, N. J. LEE and J. L. BOUVIER, Geol. Surv. Canada, Paper 74-79, 1974.
6. P. G. JEFFERY and A. A. REED, *Analyst*, 1960, **85**, 478.
7. J. N. WALSH, *Analyst*, 1977, **102**, 51-54.
8. J. D. H. STRICKLAND, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 862-876.
9. G. J. S. GOVETT, *Analytica Chim. Acta*, 1961, **25**, 69.
10. I. R. MORRISON and A. L. WILSON, *Analyst*, 1963, **88**, 88.
11. A. RINGBON, *et al*, *Analytica Chim. Acta*, 1959, **20**, 78.
12. P. M. BAKER and B. R. FARRANT, *Analyst*, 1968, **93**, 732.
13. A. HALA'SZ, *et al*, *Talanta*, 1971, **18**, 557, 569, 577.
14. V. W. TRUESDALE and C. J. SMITH, *Analyst*, 1975, **100**, 203, 797, *Analyst*, 1976, **101**, 19.
15. R. A. CHALMERS and A. G. SINCLAIR, *Analytica Chim. Acta*, 1965, **33**, 384-390.
16. H. W. SWANK and M. G. MELLON, *Ind. Eng. Chem. (Anal.)*, 1934, **6**, 348.
17. W. J. YOUNG, Statistical Techniques for Collaborative Tests, Assoc. Official Anal. Chem. Washington, 1967.
18. O. A. OHLWILER, *et al*, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **61**, 57.
19. F. J. FLANAGAN, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 1973, **37**, 1189.